

Data Management Plan

Project Title

Correlating World Conflict with Local Economy Growth

Project Abstract

For the average student, the [Uppsala Conflict Data Program <https://ucdp.uu.se/>](https://ucdp.uu.se/) offers a fascinating periscope onto the conflicts of the world. Together with economic figures as collected by [Statistik Austria <https://www.statistik.at>](https://www.statistik.at), the local economic impact of world-wide conflict is calculated.

Public Project Repository DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4699809>

Public Project Repository URL

<https://github.com/qyanu/2021-gdp-vs-ucdp>

Creator

Max-Julian Pogner <max-julian@pogner.at>, a student at [TU Wien <https://tuwien.ac.at>](https://tuwien.ac.at) (**without endorsement** on the part of *TU Wien*).

Organization

The author of this project acts in his own right.

DMP Template

Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management (Extended Edition with DMP Evaluation Rubric), Science Europe, January 2021, https://www.scienceurope.org/media/4brkxxe5/se_rdm_practical_guide_extended_final.pdf

DMP DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4699776>

Last Modified

19. April 2021

1. DATA DESCRIPTION AND COLLECTION OR RE-USE OF EXISTING DATA

This section describes how data collection is performed respectively can be re-produced, as well as describes the type, format, size and license considerations per data set. For there inseparable nature, both questions are handled together:

- 1a. How will new data be collected or produced and/or how will existing data be re-used?
- 1b. What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced?

Overview

Collected source data comes from two sources

- *ucdp-data* is from the *Uppsala Conflict Data Program* (UCDP) at Uppsala University, Sweden, via download from <https://ucdp.uu.se/downloads/> and
- *sna-at-data* is from the *Volkswirtschaftliche Gesamtrechnung* (SNA-AT) by STATISTIK AUSTRIA, Austria, via download from subpages of <https://statistik.at>.

Intermediate data is calculated based on the respective source data

- *ucdp-data-extracted* is based on *ucdp-data*, and
- *sna-at-data-extracted* is based on *sna-at-data*.

Final output data *output-data* is calculated based on both intermediate data sets.

Quick Guide

So long as access to at least the public project git repository is given, all manual steps have already been performed, and executing the steps detailed in section "How to Build" of the [README <README.pdf>](#) is sufficient. It basically boils down to executing a single bash script:

```
$ build.sh
```

Uniform project CSV

The csv data format is chosen by this project as the principal data format, as it is the most simple and most universal data format still supporting all relevant characteristics required by this project.

This data management plan often refers to a "uniform project csv" data format. This names the csv data format adopted by this project. As CSV is not formally standardized, each project has to ensure the most practical csv variation is followed.

This project elects to follow the csv format as used by the python3.7 module `csv` to maximize machine-processability as well as ensuring a widely adopted csv variation is used.

Of specific remark are the following properties of the "uniform project csv" data format:

- produced csv files always have column labels as first row.
- produced csv files never contains the newline character "\n" within cell values.
- number values are rendered in a machine-friendly format, with dot '.' decimal separator and no thousands separator.
- date and time values are rendered as ISO8601 (e.g. *YYYY-MM-DD*)

SNA-AT Source Data from Statistik Austria

SNA-AT data from Statistik Austria has to be downloaded manually, and is then preserved in the directory *sna-at-data* of the project git repository.

This data set itself is tabular numeric data, split into multiple parts, and wrapped in inconvenient container formats *pdf* and *xlsx*. The contained information is concerned with the numeric calculation of common key economic indicators.

If the download has already been performed, the previously downloaded data can already be found stored in that directory. A (re-)download is/was performed according to the steps laid out in the document [Manual SNA-AT Downloading <code/sna-at-download.pdf>](#) found in the project git repository.

Intermediate Data based on SNA-AT

SNA-AT-EXTRACTED data is manually extracted from the files within the SNA-AT data collection and manually combined, then the resulting intermediate data is preserved in the directory *sna-at-data-extracted* of the project git repository.

This data set itself is tabular numeric data, in uniform project csv format. The contained information is a merged and converted sub-set of the *sna-at* data set.

The process is detailed in the document [Manual SNA-AT Data Ingesting <code/sna-at-extract-and-combine.pdf>](#) found in the project git repository.

Source Data from UCDP

Due to license considerations, the data downloaded from UCDP cannot be stored in a public git repository. In case you have access to the non-public git repository, the data is already downloaded and stored in the directory *ucdp-data*. Otherwise, the data *must* be re-downloaded.

(Re-)download is automatically performed as a step within the general buildscript *build.sh*, but can be performed explicitly with script *code/ucdp-download.sh*. Note, that this script will compare the final acquired csv file with a known sha256 content checksum, in order to ensure an undamaged file was acquired.

The data format *csv* is chosen for its highest compatibility and highest world-wide and long-time support. The other available formats were either rejected (*xlsx* was deemed unfit, due to the almost only 100% compatible software, *Excel* likely to experience problems with some data-sets provided by the UCDP, including the subject data set), or un-preferred (*RData* and *STATA* due to less expected compatibility and providing features not required by this project).

This data set itself is tabular numeric, labelling and categorizing data, in *ucdp csv* format.

Intermediate Data based on UCDP

Due to license considerations, the data extracted and aggregated from the UCDP data cannot be stored in a public git repository. In case you have access to the non-public git repository, the data is already extracted and aggregated and stored in the directory *ucdp-data-extracted*. Otherwise, the data *must* be re-processed to acquire the *ucdp-data-extracted* data.

ucdp-data-extracted data is automatically extracted and aggregated as a step within the general buildscript *build.sh*, but can be performed explicitly with script *code/ucdp-extract.py*. This script will read the *ucdp* data from the directory *ucdp-data*, process it, and put the result intermediate data set *ucdp-extracted* data in directory *ucdp-data-extracted*.

This data set itself is tabular numeric data, in uniform project csv format.

Output Data

Due to license considerations, the final output data cannot be stored in a public git repository. In case you have access to the non-public git repository, the data is already calculated and stored in the directory *output-data*. Otherwise, the data *must* be re-calculated.

output data is automatically calculated as a step within the general buildscript *build.sh*, but calculations can be performed explicitly with script *code/cross.py*. This script will read the *ucdp-extracted* and *sna-at-extracted* data set, and process them, and put the resulting *output* data set into the *output-data* directory.

This output data itself is a correlation-*xy*-plot, with all points stored in uniform project *csv* format.

The data points are additionally rendered as *pdf* format form human consumption, but the rendering strictly contains only information also contained within the *csv* format.

Overall Data Volume

Total cumulative data size settles just below 10 MB, and if the calculations of this project are repeated at a later time, the upper bound of data volume is expected to follow a linear growth model with circa 1.1 MB additional each year.

Methodology of Reproducibility

All operations on the data are implemented using scripts and programs, or are undertaken manually by a human according to a step-by-step guide if programmatic processing is not possible. The main scripts and programs should not require any parameters.

By excluding other venues of data retrieval or data processing, all such actions are automatically reproducible.

A single top-level *build.sh* script is provided to offer an easy way to re-perform all automateable actions, ensuring that after *build.sh* has been successfully executed, all artifacts correspond to a consistent state and contain their respective reproducible content.

This method also provides documentation of the individual data collection and processing steps, as per community conventions and traditions (cf. the proverb *read the source!*). Albeit, the quality of documentation is subject to the ability of the source code writer to produce readable and well-structured source code (A feat which includes providing a clear, coherent and thorough description of the function and purpose of each script or program near the very beginning of the respective source code files) and the ability of the person interested in making use of the documentation to read source code files in the respective scripting or programming language.

Data Preservation

For data preservation and reproducibility purposes, the code, the source data, the intermediate data, the output data as well as all auxilliary build artifacts (such as the pdf rendering of this data management plan) are all stored within the same project git repository.

Due to the magnitude of data overall size, this approach is feasible. This approach is also advisable and practical, as reducing the number of different places and packaging everything nicely together increases later findability and aides in long-term preservation of the project in a functional form.

For the purpose of licensing (see below) a distinction between public and non-public copies of the project git repository is made. While non-public data sets cannot be preserved in a public copy of the git repository, the automatic general buildscript offers easy download of the non-public parts. Non-public project git repository/-ies contain all data.

Data Licensing

The data from UCDP and STATISTIK AUSTRIA have to be treated separately, from a license perspective.

Data from STATISTIK AUSTRIA is marked with a clear license statement, effectively consenting to a wide range of activities, including re-publishing of the original data as well as re-publishing of extractions of and derivative works based on the data. Certain provisions to attach specific remarks and notes to re-publications, extractions and derivative works must be observed.

Data from the UCDP lacks a clear copyright or license statement. The download page (the webpage where download to the data is offered) does not make any copyright or license statements, nor is such statement included in the downloaded data set. And while the public restrictionless downloadability of the UCDP data set can be legally construed as consenting to unlimited downloading, inspecting and locally using all data from the UCDP, as far as this author without any legal education knows, cannot be treated any form of agreement to re-publishing the data;

As a consequence, such the data sets consisting of or being based on the UCDP data is treated as non-public by this project.

Specifically the data sets *sna-at-data* and *sna-at-data-extracted* bear the license from STATISTIK AUSTRIA and is marked public. The data sets *ucdp-data* and *ucdp-data-extracted* do not bear a license permitting re-publishing and is marked non-public. The data set *output-data*, being principally based on both source data sets, has unclear license status and is marked non-public. Code and auxiliary files in this project, fully created by the project team, will be separately licensed and is marked public.

The differing license situations of the individual parts of this project are clearly documented/issued in the *LICENSE* files in the respective (sub-)directories.

2. DOCUMENTATION AND DATA QUALITY

2a. What metadata and documentation (for example the methodology of data collection and way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Each data set, as well as the code, has associated meta-data in a file `META.xml`. The filename was chosen to follow the tradition and convention of storing meta-data, such as `LICENSE`, `TODO`, etc, in files with all-caps naming, if either the principal data does not support embedded meta-data, or such embedding is deemed impractical.

The `META.xml` files contain meta-data compliant with `simpledc.xsd` as published by the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative, with as many terms from <https://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dc.xsd> filled with values as was meaningful. Validity of all `META.xml` files can be verified with script `code/meta-verify.sh`.

This author's upbringing is somewhat overlapping with the conventions and traditions predominant within the Open Source Software-Development Community. Not incidentally, this project commit to observe and refine these informal standards and common processes. As such

- versioning, insofar as a new version of a data or files semantically replaces the previous version, is handled through the usage of a git repository,
- common meta-data is stored in files with all-caps and well-known filenames (with an optional additional lower-case file extension) such as `README`, `LICENSE`, etc,
- performed steps are clearly and reproducibly documented by way of source code,
- source code follows the principles of nice-to-read and clear-structured, beyond the functionally necessary,
 - for example, each script and program source code must have a description of it's purpose and function near the very beginning of it's content.
- binary or other source formats not easily readable by means of simple text editor are discouraged, maximizing compatibility and machine-actionability of source code files with future iterations of the software tools landscape.
 - for example with this reasoning, this Data Management Plan is **not** written using the **DMP-Online** tool for it's lack of compatibility with a wide range of editors (namely only a single homepage can be used) as well as difficulties to track edit changes through a version control system such as git.
 - with similar reasoning, the **reStructuredText** (`rst`) format is preferred by the relevant community over the *Markdown* (`md`) format en-vogue in some adjacent communities, due to Markdown suffering from the same problems as `csv`; in contrast to `md` (with multiple entities publishing partially conflicting specification, in addition to not being well-defined in the mathematical sense), `rst` is syntactically and semantically well-defined, does not suffer from certain security flaws (e.g. remote-code execution when viewing a `md` document, if the viewer does not exhibit the most zealous of input validation, in contrast of `rst` avoiding such parser problems already at the average input validation level).
- and many other implicitly followed best practices.

A note on directory structure

Files with well-known purpose receive their respective well-known names in all-caps, plus an optional lower-case file type and format extension. Specifically this concerns the files `LICENSE`, `README.rst` and similar.

This project's main division of content is by data-set/code into (sub-)directories. The names of directories are, disregarding encoding intricacies (e.g. avoidance of whitespaces), identical to the names of the respective data sets or project parts.

- `code/` contains scripts, program source code and auxiliary files created by this project team, only of interest to a person either editing the project, or interested in the project in a similar degree. Files in this directory are public.
- `output-data/` contains final output data set. An unknown license applies. Files in this directory are therefore non-public.
- `sna-at-data/` contains the data as downloaded from STATISTIK AUSTRIA. Their license statement applies. Files in this directory are publishable.
- `sna-at-data-extracted/` contains the merged, filtered and extracted sub-data set from the *sna-at-data* data. As this is a derivative work of *sna-at-data*, the same license statement from STATISTIK AUSTRIA applies. Files in this directory are publishable.
- `ucdp-data/` contains the data as downloaded from UCDP. As no license statement was given by UCDP, this data must not be re-published. Files in this directory are therefore non-public.
- `ucdp-data-extracted/` contains processed data result of the UCDP data set. As this is a derivative work of *ucdp-data*, the same license considerations apply. Files in this directory are therefore non-public.
- `/` contains such files as are of primary interest to a first-time casual reader of the project. All files are created by this project team and are public.

As the number of items per directory already reaches non-excessive magnitude, and recalling the fact that humans find deep-nested directory structures less easy to work with than flat structures (so long as the number of items does not become excessive), no further sub-divisions are performed.

This sub-division of the project files conveniently also arranges the files according to the respective licensing situation.

A note on file naming

Versioning of files is handled by the built-in features of a git repository, and the default concept of git is followed in this respect. No version information is included as part of file names, so long as a new version of a file semantically replaces earlier versions of that file.

In the directories replicating the source data collected from external source (*sna-at-data* and *ucdp-data*), the exact file naming as used by the external source is preserved. This way a later reader of the project can more easily trace which data exactly were downloaded.

All meta-data also managed by the git repository, such as researcher name, date of edits, etc, are treated equivalent to versioning described above, and therefore are also not included in file names.

Whitespaces and special symbols are avoided. In order to not crash windows machines, certain names are prohibited: `aux`, `con`, `com`, etc.

Note: The file naming conventions detailed in this documented have been informed by <https://datamanagement.hms.harvard.edu/collect/file-naming-conventions>.

Naming of data sets

The data sets were intentionally named, such that a first-time reader can easily discern relationships (*-data* => *-data-extracted*), stage ("output") or category (*sna-at* vs *ucdp*).

A note on versioning in public repositories

For the purpose of making the project git repository publicly available, *squashing* the git repository might be decided to be done by the project stakeholders, out of consideration for privacy (in order to not publish at which times of day a particular project team member has worked on the project), security (in order to not publish critical bits of information that erroneously were committed and then deleted), or public relations (in order to not publicly present information that might be utilized by a malevolent third party). In this case,

- the content (`commit^{tree}`) before and after the squashing must be verified to be byte-by-byte equal.
- the correspondence of private git repository version with squashed public git repository version is tracked using mechanisms already built-in into the git repository.

2b. What data quality control measures will be used?

Due to the limited size and scope of the project, and the absence of any other person that participate in this project, relying on the good practices of the author seems unavoidable. Peer review or four-eyes principle is unattainable.

Regarding the quality of data itself, no domain-specific knowledge for the two data sets exist within the project team for the domains of conflict data or country economic data.

"layman-knowledge" can be applied for the verification of data,

- after the downloading step (at the source data sets),
- after part of the processing was performed (at the intermediate data sets),
- after complete processing has finished (at the output data set).

The verification is already part of the step-by-step guides for manual data collection, extraction and merging (see files [code/sna-at-download.pdf](#), [code/sna-at-extract-and-combine.pdf](#)), and additional verification checklists are pointed to by section in the README (see [README.rst](#) section "How to Build", pointing to [code/ucdp-quality-checklist.pdf](#)) that also the most casual reader of this project must encounter -- It is supposed that users who do not even read the "How to Build" section of the README would also never follow pointers to, or perform steps recommended by, a data quality checklist.

By placing the checklists (or pointer to them) at places where a user performing or invoking a data collection or data processing, it is hoped that an interested user is reminded of their presence just at the most convenient time.

"layman-knowledge" verification is performed through aforementioned checklists according to the following principles:

- numerical magnitude and range of values is known.
- interpretation (whether they indicate data errors or are expected in a normal data set) of outliers is not possible --

For example to verify that the impact of major historical events such as the collapse of the soviet union, the ascension of EU membership of Austria, the 2008 crisis of the EU financial sector and currently the Covid-19 pandemic is duly reflected in the respective data sets, would require more-than-layman knowledge of the respective domain.

- humans more easily recognize patterns or anti-patterns on visualizations of data (e.g. graphs), compared to looking at the csv data directly.

The content of the data verification checklists was informed by reading of <https://old.dataone.org/best-practices/quality>, which was recommended by aforementioned DMP-Online webpage. From that source, the following considerations decidedly do not apply to this project.

Consider the compatibility of the data you are integrating

The output data principally consists of a x-y-scatter plot, explicitly designed to support compatible as well as incompatible data, so long as the data for each axis is sortable in some capacity.

Identify outliers

For the considerations laid out in the content of this section so far, the means are missing to decide whether outliers are indication of error or normal.

3. STORAGE AND BACKUP DURING THE RESEARCH PROCESS

3a. How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

In general, handling of data and program source code is undertaken on the *Pogner Family IT Infrastructure* (from now on called "pogitsys").

A full copy of the project git repository is hosted as git repository on pogitsys as part of the 'active data' storage. This full copy includes at least the non-public and public variant of the git repository.

Insofar as data and program source code is designated as public-access according to the previous section of this document (that is, all parts except ones marked as non-public), a mirror of the public project git repository is hosted and published on github.com.

As the project does not making any arrangements regarding backup, etc., the default arrangements of pogitsys are in effect, as detailed in this chapter.

It is the responsibility of each project team member, to perform *commit and push* (one of the most basic *git* functions) in a timely fashion after each project edit. Only when *commit and push* has been performed by the respective project team member, the services offered by pogitsys spring into action.

Pogitsys is a robust, highly automated it infrastructure providing a range of services to authorized users, the Pogner family members. Clear policies are defined by the sysadmin team under guidance of the chief sysadmin, and carried out by the sysadmin of the day. Policies exist for a wide range of subjects, such as which services to provide, what responsibility is taken up by the it-infrastructure and what responsibility is taken up by the user, and what level of various services are provided.

Implemented policies include automated regular on-site and off-site backup as well as append-only archivation of the 'active data' storage. Service level guarantees an absolute maximum of 24h delay (with an average delay of 6h) between some data stored, changed or deleted on the 'active data' storage and that store, change or delete being recorded in the 'archive data' storage and propagated to both 'on-site backup data' and 'off-site backup data' storages.

3b. How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

Who will be responsible for backup and recovery?

The individual project team members are responsible

- a. to include all project source code, data and auxilliary files in the git repository.
- b. to 'commit & push' in a timely fashion.

As long as the git repository itself remains intact, the project team is responsible to manage any and all data stored within the git repository. This includes reverting to a previous version, merging multiple conflicting versions, or recovering a deleted or damaged file which is still stored in a different or previous version.

The sysadmin team is responsible to continually improve policies, to provide services as prescribed in said policies and to offer training to all pogitsys users.

The sysadmin team is also responsible to implement the necessary automated processes, such that any and all data from the 'active data' storage is continually backed up to backup storage and archived to archive storage, with the maximum delay times prescribed in the policies.

The sysadmin of the day is responsible to effect recovery procedures, either sparked by a user request (e.g. inadvertant damaging the git repository) or as response to an it-infrastructure incident.

How will the data be recovered in the event of an incident?

The steps taken to recover from an incident are highly individual to each incident. Generally speaking the following phases occur.

First, the sysadmin of the day follows the procedures laid out by the sysadmin team, to reinstate the services offered by the it-infrastructure. This includes re-installing damaged services, ordering replacement hardware, or identifying that external it-security experts are required to recover from a particular incident and coordinating with such external consultants.

Then the sysadmin reverts to his/her normal role of assisting users, should they request recovery of certain data data from the data-archive or data-backup.

The project team is responsible to return the project git repository into good order. But this is expected to only consist of verifying good order, or requesting appropriate backup-recovery from the sysadmin.

And lastly, when the inevitable death of the master sysadmin (this author) has eventuated, instructions are laid out in the will and testament, protected by Shamir's Secret Sharing, how to securely transfer the chief sysadmin role to any successor.

What are the risks to data security and how will these be managed?

The main risk is accidental data loss or data corruption by a user inadvertently commanding his/her computer to perform some action. This main risk is managed by maintaining the data-archive, which has does not perform any real delete function during normal operation (instead data is merely marked).

The second greatest risk posed by generic worms, viruses and other malware, is mitigated by the data-archive and data-backup be performed on dedicated machines with the minimal amount of software necessary to perform their function. Access to these machines is only granted through a special procedure, as also any sysadmin is subject to the abovementioned main risk. Of the software available to conduct the functions of the data-backup and data-archive, after carefully comparing the choices, the software with the highest likelihood of small attack surface, highest long-term stability and long-term bugfix support is selected.

The third greatest risk are posed by attacks specifically undertaken to target a specific person associated with the it-infrastructure or the it-infrastructure itself. This risk is accepted as not preventable with the available resources, and worst-case outcome is possible in this case.

How will you control access to keep the data secure?

Under normal operations, access to the non-public git repository is restricted to users that are

- a. registered with the it-infrastructure
- b. registered with the project

The sysadmin of the day is responsible for granting or revoking access.

Project team is responsible of a timely report to the Sysadmin, if new project team members join or project team members leave.

The public repository at github.com grants read access to all users and all third parties. Write access is restricted to this author only.

How will you ensure that collaborators can access your data securely?

The git repository is accessibly only via the `git+ssh` method, and as such is protected by the secure `ssh` protocol.

The git repository is hosted on a server with 24/7 planned uptime and proper internet connection, so any collaborator can access the git repository at a time of his/her choosing.

If creating or collecting data in the field how will you ensure its safe transfer into your main secured systems?

While this does not apply to this project, the theoretical answer is as follows.

Project team member personal computers can edit and commit all content stored in the git repository at all times (such is the feature offered by *git*). However, for pushing one's changed to the it-infrastructure, and thereby (a) making the edits available to all other project team members, and (b) ensuring the proper backup and archive of the new edit, a stable internet connection is required.

Each project team member is responsible for arrange for an internet connection and pushing edits, in due course. (cf. the push-at-end-of-day policy)

4. LEGAL AND ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS, CODES OF CONDUCT

4a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

All data sets are not in relation, and are not relateable through auxilliary data sets, to individual persons or small groups of persons. All datasets can be truely regarded as anonymous with respect to personal data. Therefore, considerations for the GDPR and similar do not apply.

The data sets do not contain sensitive data in the privacy/ethical sense.

4b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

What copyright is applicable?

In case of the SNA-AT data from Statistik Austria, legal permission for usage, preservation and re-publishing (and further actions) was given through the license statement afixed to the respective webpage from where the data was downloaded.

There was no visible indication, that the webpage incorrectly displayed wrong content, or that the webpage was not from Statistik Austria. The url was verified to be a subpage of <https://statistik.at/> or <https://www.statistik.at/>.

In case of the UCDP/PRIO data from the UCDP, no license statement accompanied the downloaded data. However, as access to the data was without any restrictions whatsoever, the files where easily findable on the internet, and the actual download sub webpage <https://ucdp.uu.se/downloads/> was easily linked from the main page <https://ucdp.uu.se/>, consent to download, use, and locally store is implicitly given. Consent to re-publish the data is assumed to be not granted, or that if the required consent for re-publishing is given is at least unclear; therefore the downloaded data cannot be re-published without further consultation.

There was no visible indication, that the webpage incorrectly displayed wrong content, or that the webpage was not from the UCDP. The url was verified to be a subpage of <https://ucdp.uu.se>.

In case of the project files wholly created by the project team, copyright and all associated rights, initially jointly lies with the project team members.

In case of the output data set, license situation is unclear, and this project acts under the assumption that publishing any part of the output data set is proscribed.

How copyright is managed?

The SNA-AT and SNA-AT-EXTRACTED data sets are re-published under the conditions laid out by STATISTIK AUSTRIA; specifically the source data as downloaded is re-published unchanged, and the derived intermediate data set is published having the prescribed notes affixed.

The UCDP, UCDP-EXTRACTED and OUTPUT data sets are not published, but only retained in non-public copied of the project git repository.

The scripts, program source codes, and auxilliary files are published with a CC0 license statement affixed to them (file `LICENSE` in the project root directory).

4c. What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

All data sets are either concerned with economic figures in relation to nation states, or are concerned with conflict intensity levels in relation to nation states.

The only thinkable ethical issue applying would be whether such data or the performed analysis is subject to national security considerations.

However, as the data sources STATISTIK AUSTRIA is a state-operated agency itself, and the Uppsala University can be said to be in good standing with its home state, and no controversy exists regarding the source, nature or content of the data sets, matters of national security are concluded to not be imaginable.

5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

5a. How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

Discoverability

Any third-party "surfing" to the github copy of the project repository will have immediately full read access to all public parts of the project, including the immediate rendering of the file `README.rst` which includes at the beginning the first overview-summary of the project and furthermore pointers to other parts of the project.

There are no special provisions to advertise the existence of this data set. In general, at least one other person is *following me* on github.com, any such person is expected to get notified by github.com on uploading the public part of repository to github.com.

General findability through the de-facto exclusive search engine Google is likely, but will probably be restricted to only the most specific search queries.

This approach follows the intended exposure for this project.

Long-Term Preservation

The public git repository hosted at github.com will be retained as long as possible, subject to policy changed on the part of Microsoft Inc, the entity effectively controlling the strategic planning of github.com.

The full project git repository will be preserved until a catastrophic event destroys the pogitsys it-infrastructure (e.g. a sudden and hyper-expansive raise in hardware prices or other a targeted it-security attack).

Data publication timeline

The public project git repository is scheduled to be uploaded to github.com at or shortly before Monday, 19th April 2021, 23:59 CEST. From that time of upload onwards, any third-party "finding" the github project page will have full read access.

The full project git repository hosted on the pogitsys infrastructure was already continuous made available to all authorized users from the outset of the project.

The private parts will not be published. However, a reader can perform the easy to use general buildscript *build.sh* in order to acquire his/her own copy of the UCDP source data set and derived intermediate data set.

Reusability of the project parts

Any third-party establishing read-access to the project repository, based on the various license statements, will be able to reuse the various project parts under their respective license:

- the sna-at parts under the terms as layed out by STATISTIK AUSTRIA
- all parts wholly created by the project team under the CC0 permissive license.

The parts 'tainted' with ucdp data will only be useable to a third-party after executing the respective download script, or the general buildscript *build.sh*.

5b. How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term (for example a data repository or archive)?

For long-term preservation, the full project repository will be left as-is on the pogitsys, which already provides backup and archive services. This decision was made by the project team.

While this author expects this project to perform purely in raising general interest in the insights offered by the UDCP, it is nevertheless the intended purpose. As such, the publication at github.com is more important than the secluded archivation within the pogitsys infrastructure.

Lacking access to relevant directories or index services, this project will not be registered with any data repository registration services. Specifically attaining access to relevant index services would exceed time resources allocated to this project and therefore will not be pursued.

The project will remain findable through google search engine and github search.

Publication at github.com will not incur any costs so long as the current strategic objectives of Microsoft Inc remain in place; an eventuality that cannot be estimated by the project team and therefore will be handled on an ad-hoc basis by this author.

Archivation on the pogitsys will incur unnoticable costs, due to the cummulative data size of the project being several orders of magnitude smaller than the regularly managed data sizes on pogitsys. The costs will be burdened on the general it-budget of the Pogner Family.

5c. What methods or software tools are needed to access and use data?

Access to the public project git repository is subject to the access methods implemented and maintained by github.com. Currently the latest version of one the big-two web browsers (Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox -- With each having many rebranded incarnations, for example the Microsoft Edge web browser) is required.

After access to the data has been established, the software listed in the `README` file (see there) under section *Build Dependencies*, or compatible software, is required to make full use of the project.

It is expected that the `csv` data format, used for all final and intermediate data produced by this project, will remain usable with a most wide range of software tools for many years to come.

5d. How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier (such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)) to each data set be ensured?

As per the recommended reading of the github guide on zenodo integration, only *public github repositories* can be issued with a DOI through the github/zenodo partnership.

Additionally, detailed inspection of of the DOI homepage <https://doi.org> indicates that one of the 10 listed DOI Registration Agencies **MUST** be used if a doi is sought to be issued for this project. However, each of the 10 agencies requires some kind of institutional relationship this author, acting under his own right without institutional endorsement, lacks.

As a result, only the following DOIs can be acquired as persistent identifiers.

- a DOI for the the main github repository will be acquired through the github/zenodo partnership.
Acquired DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4699809>
- for the *sna-at-data* and *sna-at-data-extracted* data sets, a snapshot will be each uploaded separately to zenodo to, and a separate DOI acquired for these snapshots.

A variant with git submodules replacing the directories was considered, but discarded due to that feature's major compatibility problems, including an implicit vendor lockin (the absolute inability to move the git repositories to a different hosting in the future).

- *sna-at* data set: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4699804>
- *sna-at-extracted* data set: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4699806>
- the *ucdp* and *ucdp-extracted* data sets will **not** receive DOIs, as publishing them to github as public repository is not possible, and therefore the github/zenodo partnership will not issue a DOI.

6. DATA MANAGEMENT RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

6a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

Due to the limited size of this project, a single person is charged with handling all current and future responsibilities, including those regarding data management and data stewardship, and including updating all project content such as scripts, source code, auxiliary files, data, and meta-data.

```
Max-Julian Pogner  
max-julian@pogner.at  
https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6244-0173
```

6b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

Considering the relative abundance of personal projects and overlong list of prospecting projects of this author, no resources, neither financial nor time, will be allotted to the continued availability of the public project git repository at github.com. Consequently, any external incident at github.com might take the published project offline, without being noticed.

However, due to the nature and inner workings of github.com, it is expected that the project will be available at github.com for many years to come without any efforts expended on part of this project's data steward.

If a future project should make re-use of (parts of) this project, or change parts of this project, such re-use or change will be treated as a complete new project and resource planning will restart from scratch. No resources need to be earmarked for this eventuality with respect to this project's resource planning.

Long-term personal archive will be ensured through general service level provided by pogitsys. If the data steward should become aware, despite expending zero resources into relevant monitoring activities, that the data from github.com became unpublished, it would be very little effort to re-publish the project.